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A systematic review to examine approaches used for engaging children and young people in digital psychotherapy interventions

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Citation

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Review question

1. What approaches are used for engaging children and young people with mental health problems in digital interventions?
2. What are the barriers and facilitators to engaging children and young people with mental health problems in digital health interventions?
3. How recruitment and retention rates vary in digital intervention research involving children and young people with mental health problems?

Searches

We will undertake an electronic search of the following databases: PubMed, MEDLINE, Cochrane Library, PsycINFO, Web of Science and Scopus, in addition to hand searching of the Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, and the Journal of Medical Internet Research. We will use Boolean operators to search for a list of pre-specified search terms in titles and abstracts. The search strategy will not be limited to peer-reviewed journals, but will include relevant materials in the grey literature.

Types of study to be included

We will include research in various languages and study types including those identified through the grey literature.

Condition or domain being studied

The review will explore studies involving children and young people with mental health disorders.

Participants/population

Children (0-18) and young people (15-24) diagnosed with mental health disorders. i.e. Studies presenting data for participants with a mental health diagnosis, above cut off points on a diagnostic mental health questionnaire or those accessing mental health treatment.

Intervention(s), exposure(s)

Primary research involving the development or evaluation of digital interventions used adjunct to/instead of face-to-face therapy where:

- 1) reducing mental health difficulties is the executive goal;
- 2) there is provision of an interventions via digital platforms including smartphone applications and websites but not only for communication purposes e.g. neither telehealth, nor appointment reminders;
- 3) it is not lab based only but used in real world settings.

Comparator(s)/control

Not applicable.

Context

We will include research conducted in any setting including those carried out at in-patient hospitals, outpatient clinics or schools.

Main outcome(s)

The aim of the review is to identify approaches used to engage children and young people in digital psychotherapy interventions. Our primary outcome would be adherence to treatment.

Timing and effect measures

Additional outcome(s)

- Recruitment and retention rates.
- Acceptability of approaches to engage children and young people in digital psychotherapy interventions.
- Barriers and facilitators to engaging children and young people in digital psychotherapy interventions.

Timing and effect measures

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Two reviewers will conduct the selection and coding of studies and the remaining reviewers will be involved in resolving any disagreements. All reviewers will be involved in reaching a consensus on the data to be extracted and the terminology used for engagement/involvement before the start of screening. Data to be extracted includes the following: author and year, study design, participants (including sample size, age, gender), main presenting problems, intervention, approaches used to engage children/young people in using the digital intervention, recruitment and retention, acceptability of approaches, and barriers and facilitators.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

As the primary aim of this systematic review is to identify approaches used to engage children and young people in digital psychotherapy interventions, a risk of bias assessment may not be applicable. However, if there is a subset of eligible studies where this can be applied, we will use published bias assessment tools (e.g., Cochrane risk of bias assessment).

Strategy for data synthesis

We will undertake a narrative synthesis to present and explain our findings with basic numerical analysis of the extent, nature, and distribution of the studies included in the review. We aim to use the RevMan software as the overall review manager with input from all named researchers on this review with additional reviewers to resolve any discrepancies during the selection and data extraction process. We will analyze aggregate quantitative and descriptive data to inform themes for our discussion.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None.

Contact details for further information

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Collaborators

. TEAM: Technology Enabled Mental Health for Young People

. TREATME: European Network on Individualized Psychotherapy Treatment of Young People with Mental Disorders

Type and method of review

Systematic review

Anticipated or actual start date

01 May 2018

Anticipated completion date

31 August 2019

Funding sources/sponsors

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Conflicts of interest

Language

English, Hebrew, Portuguese-Local, Romanian, Spanish

Country

England, Israel, Portugal, Spain

Stage of review

Review Ongoing

Subject index terms status

Subject indexing assigned by CRD

Subject index terms

Child; Humans; Psychotherapy

Date of registration in PROSPERO

01 June 2018

Date of publication of this version

15 April 2019

Details of any existing review of the same topic by the same authors

Stage of review at time of this submission

Stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	Yes
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	Yes	Yes
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

Versions

01 June 2018

13 June 2018

15 April 2019

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This information has been provided by the named contact for this review. CRD has accepted this information in good faith and registered the review in PROSPERO. The registrant confirms that the information supplied for this submission is accurate and complete. CRD bears no responsibility or liability for the content of this registration record, any associated files or external websites.